

PHONOLOGICAL SIMILARITIES BETWEEN TAGALOG AND BAHASA INDONESIA USING PHONOLOGY AS HUMAN BEHAVIOR (PHB)

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia using Phonology as Human Behavior by William Diver. Phonology as human behavior is a theory attributed to American linguist and Columbia School of Linguistics founder William Diver. Philippines and Indonesia have diverse linguistic cultures, they both belong to the Austronesian language family, however, it is noticeable that these countries share more similarities compared to other countries from the Austronesian language. Using textual analysis within the lens of Phonology as Human Behavior, this paper finds out the Phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesia in terms of alphabet, common words for daily use, vowel phonemes and most importantly Stress and Unstressed Syllable patterns. This paper offers a comprehensive explanation of why Tagalog and Indonesian possessed phonological similarities in terms of syllable structures. Therefore, this paper concludes that the Philippines and Indonesia not only share a similar geographic demography, but also share common phonological patterns.

Keywords: *Phonology, Filipino Linguistics, Indonesian Linguistics, Southeast Asian Dialects, Phonology as Human Behavior*

INTRODUCTION

This study examines the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia using William Diver's (1979) Theory of Phonology as Human Behavior. As an Austronesian language, this hypothesis is applied to study the similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. Languages of different countries differ. There are many different language families spoken by communities, especially in Asia. As stated by Raymunde et al. (2023) The Austronesian language family is one of the language families spoken in Asia.

The Austronesian language family with over 170 recognized languages, including Tagalog, Bikol, Cebuano, Ilocano, Kapampangan, Pangasinense, and Waray, the Philippines is home to a diverse group of people, including traders from China, colonists from North America and Europe, and voyagers from other continents (Lois, 2020). However, the Filipino language, despite its strong Austronesian influences, is considered further distant from the original Austronesia language family than its counterparts from Indonesia, Malay, and the Timor Islands. It all started historically in the ninth century when the last Indianized kingdom in Indonesia, the Majapahit empire, made its way to the Philippine islands.

The spoken dialects of the Philippines and Indonesia are related and descended from the same linguistic culture, as they are both members of the Malayo-Polynesian branch of the Austronesian language family. Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia encompass distinct meanings for some phrases, even when speakers of their respective languages communicate or interact with one another in their own spoken languages, uncertainty and misunderstanding of some words still occur. As stated in the study of Lim (2017), Both Indonesia and the Philippines are archipelagic nations with a similar ethnic population of Austronesian descent. The Philippines and ancient Indonesia have a long history dating back to the 9th century. Tagalog is a well-known descendent of the Malayo-Polynesian subgroup.

As stated in the study of Potet (2018), The Tagalog language [ta:ga:log] is composed of two bases: tagá, which means "native of" and álog denotes "ford". Consequently, it indicates "vadean" from Latin vādum which also means "ford". That's why it transformed into "tagalo" in Spanish, where the latest can be primarily dental, which caused the removal of /g/. Once combined, the persisting final -o was demonstrated as the mark of the "manlike" or "masculine", while the "women like" or "feminine" means tagala, e.g. El tagalo or "Tagalog", and La lengua tagala which means "The Tagalog Language". However, The Bahasa Indonesia was proclaimed as the sovereign language of Indonesia in the early 1920's by the nationalist movement there. The name Bahasa Indonesia refers to the Indonesian language. This language belongs to the Austronesian family of languages and is mostly descended from Malay (Wrihatni & Sutami, 2019).

In comparison, both languages—Tagalog and Indonesian—have something in common in terms of linguistic traits. For instance, the word "mahal" in translation in Tagalog means "expensive" or "love," while in Indonesia it also means "expensive" or "highly expensive"; moreover, some words have the same meaning as well as similar syllable structures. In addition to this fact about their similarity, there are also the differences in which words still have the same meanings as well as their vowel phonemes that determine the similarity of Tagalog and Indonesian languages to each other in terms of phonology.

The Tagalog word *ako*, which means "I," is spoken and spelled "*Aku*" in Indonesian (Arizo et al., 2020). The Tagalog language has five vowel phonemes: /a/, /e/, /i/, /o/, and /u/. The two back vowels, /o/ and /u/, and the two front vowels, /e/ and /i/, were previously considered allophones because of the influence of word borrowing. This, however, altered as a result of considerable foreign interaction and word borrowing (Schachter & Otones, 1983).

According to Adelaar and Himmelmann (2004), Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia are both members of the Austronesian language family. It should be noted that some terms are synonymous in both languages. Certain words in written Bahasa Indonesia and Tagalog also have the same appearance. According to Lois (2020) certain words written in Tagalog have the vowel "o," yet words written in Bahasa Indonesia have the vowel "u." Although there are significant spelling and phonetic variations, they are similar enough to be recognised as members of the same language family. Despite the fact that they have a lot of similarity in terms of stress, using diacritical marks is considered a discernible variation. According to Almario and Kilates (2015), diacritical markings are used to indicate which syllable has to be stressed or unstressed is essential when speaking Filipino. Three diacritical points are used in Filipino orthography: *pakupyá* (circumflex), *paiwa* (grave), and *pahilis* (acute).

According to Conde (2021) even while there are clear parallels between them, they are not quite in line. This explains the significant influence of English and Spanish in Tagalog. The Philippines was colonized for 333 years by Spain and the United States. Meanwhile, many loanwords in Bahasa Indonesia can be linked to the Dutch language because of Indonesia's history as a Dutch colony.

This study aims to explore the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. It also aids in our understanding of how speech sounds can be employed to convey meaning within a single language or between languages. It also establishes how Tagalog and Indonesian phonological behaviors influence communication.

Research Questions

This study aims to know the following:

1. What are the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia?
2. How Phonology as Human Behavior explains the similarities between Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia?

METHODOLOGY

To evaluate and discuss the research problems, this study employs phonological analysis as a human behavior theory. Phonology as human behavior is a theory attributed to American linguist and Columbia School of Linguistics founder William Diver. The phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian were examined using the Lens of Phonology as Human Behaviour (PHB) by William Diver as a framework for this study. Examining how both languages use syllable structures and evaluating stress patterns to have a broader understanding of how prominent and powerful the sound is for effective communication. In order to have a comprehensive understanding of the similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian phonetics, this paper tends to evaluate the phonological similarities of two languages using the theory of phonology as human behavior (PHB).

This study evaluates the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian languages, as well as to provide the necessary information or knowledge that will benefit those who use this kind of method and that will be useful for gathering data, including as a reference for research purposes.

The Theory of Phonology as Human Behavior (PHB) is thoroughly examined in the study using the Textual Analysis method. This theory can be used to analyze the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. It does this by using textual analysis, where the content of William Diver's work is chosen using the Purposive Sampling technique. In order to make the most practical use of this study, the researchers will look at the phonological structure of how they accurately conveyed the language they use for communication. To evaluate this research, researchers will primarily use William Diver's concept of Phonology as Human Behaviour (PHB) to analyze the phonological similarities between the languages of Tagalog and Indonesia.

For this reason, phonology as human behavior is being used in this study. Phonology as Human Behaviour claims that its main contribution is that it gives an explanation and a motivation for how sounds are distributed throughout the speech signal. According to William Diver (1979), it explains why the distribution of speech segments or phonemes within language in general, and within developmental and clinical phonology in particular, is non-random. It can be done to assess the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian by using phonology as an excellent lens to investigate human behavior.

The theory of Phonology as Human Behavior provides many advantages, including the ability to comprehend sound patterns in an organized manner, the ability to compare languages in depth, the improvement of developmental and clinical phonology, and the ability to inform theoretical and practical development. As stated by Tobin (2009) it is a valuable tool for learning more about the functions of phonological systems and how they enhance effective communication.

The theory suggests that while Tagalog and Indonesian share certain similarities, they also differ. The theory of phonology as human (PHB) seeks to evaluate the phonological

similarities between two languages, Tagalog and Indonesian. The Theory of Phonology as Human Behaviour (PHB) helps the researchers to attain the comprehensive result of this study. Seemingly, the lens of phonology as human behavior (PHB) is accurate for evaluating the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian.

This study was conducted a week ago, when the researchers attempted to look into the research gap in phonological linguistic research in the Philippines. The researchers recognised that it was vital for a study paper to examine and clarify the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian.

RESULTS

To further explore how the phonological characteristics of both languages contribute to the above-mentioned discussion and successful communication, this study tends to use the notion of phonology as human behavior to explore the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. The researchers will examine the phonological structure of how they accurately conveyed the language they use for efficient communication in order to make the most practical use of this study. It also seeks to analyze the Phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian.

The theory of phonology as human behavior (PHB) is based on the definition of language as a symbolic tool, whose structure is shaped by both its communication function and the characteristics of its users (Tobin, 2009). It also suggests that language represents a compromise in the struggle to achieve maximum communication with the least amount of effort. The major contribution of PHB is in its capacity to elucidate and justify the distribution of sounds within the speech signal, or alternatively, the reasons behind the distribution of phonemes or speech segments in language as a whole (Tobin, 2009).

Modern Tagalog and Indonesian (Bahasa) Alphabet

The Association of Spanish Language Academies itself discontinued the use of Ch and Ll as separate listings in alphabetical collations in 1994. Since 2010, ch and ll are no longer considered distinct letters; instead, each digraph is now treated as a sequence of two distinct characters, finding occasional use as conjoined pairs. As a result, the Philippine alphabet was reduced to 28 letters. The usage of alphabetical collations is to separate the distinct letters which are already inconsiderable and its sequence of digraph used as conjoined pairs which are reduced to the numeration of Philippine alphabet letters

Table 1. Modern Tagalog Alphabet.

Aa ey	Bb bi	Cc si	Dd di	Ee i	Ff ef	Gg dyt
Hh eyts	li ay	Jj dyey	Kk key	Ll el	Mm em	Nn en
Ññ enye	Ngng en dyi	Oo o	Pp pi	Qq kyu	Rr ar	Ss es
Tt ti	Uu yu	Vv vi	Ww dobulyu	Xx eks	Yy way	Zz zi

Table 2. Modern Indonesian Alphabet

Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee	Ff	Gg
Hh	li	Jj	Kk	Ll	Mm	Nn
Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr	Ss	Tt	Uu
Vv	Ww	Xx	Yy	Zz		

Table 3. Vowel Phonemes of Tagalog

	Front	Central	Back
<i>Upper</i>	/i/		/u/
<i>Middle</i>	/e/		/o/
<i>Lower</i>		/a/	

Table 4. Vowels Phonemes of Indonesia (Bahasa)

	Front	Central	Back
Upper	/i/		/u/
Middle	/e/	/ə/	/o/
Lower		/a/	

Table 5. Indonesian and Tagalog similar words.

Indonesian words	Tagalog words	Meaning
<i>Aku</i>	<i>Ako</i>	<i>Me/My</i>
<i>Sabun</i>	<i>Sabon</i>	<i>Soap</i>
<i>Dewata</i>	<i>Diwata</i>	<i>Fairy, Goddess, Nymph</i>
<i>Enam</i>	<i>Anim</i>	<i>Six</i>
<i>Fondasi</i>	<i>Pundasyon</i>	<i>Foundation</i>
<i>Genap</i>	<i>Ganap</i>	<i>Exact</i>
<i>Hadapan</i>	<i>Harapan</i>	<i>Infront</i>
<i>Kombinasi</i>	<i>Kombinasyon</i>	<i>Combination</i>
<i>Inggris</i>	<i>Ingles</i>	<i>English</i>

Table 6. Indonesian and Tagalog Syllable Structures

Indonesian words	Tagalog words	Two different meanings
<i>Mula</i>	<i>Mula</i>	<i>Beginning - From where</i>
<i>Batu</i>	<i>Batu</i>	<i>A stone - Throw</i>
<i>Kuta</i>	<i>Kuta</i>	<i>City - Fort</i>
<i>Langka</i>	<i>Langka</i>	<i>Rare - Jackfruit</i>
<i>Sayang</i>	<i>Sayang</i>	<i>Alas! - Too bad</i>
<i>Sumpah</i>	<i>Sumpa</i>	<i>A Curse - An Oath</i>
<i>Sikat</i>	<i>Sikat</i>	<i>A brush - Popular</i>
<i>Yoyo</i>	<i>Yoyo</i>	<i>A stupid person - A spin toy</i>

Table 7. Indonesian and Tagalog, Stressed & Unstressed Sound Syllable Patterns.

Indonesian words	Tagalog words	Stressed	Unstressed	Meaning
<i>Aku</i>	<i>Ako</i>	<i>A-ku (stressed word/ku/)</i>	<i>A-ko (unstressed word/a/)</i>	<i>Me/My</i>
<i>Kurang</i>	<i>Kulang</i>	<i>Ku-rang (stressed word/lang/)</i>	<i>Ku-lang (Unstressed word /ku/)</i>	<i>Less</i>
<i>Bangun</i>	<i>Bangon</i>	<i>Ba-ngun (stressed word/ngun/)</i>	<i>Ba-ngon (Unstressed word /ba/)</i>	<i>Wake up</i>
<i>Laut</i>	<i>Laot</i>	<i>La-ot (stressed word/ot/)</i>	<i>La-ot (Unstressed word /la/)</i>	<i>Sea</i>
<i>Sinar</i>	<i>Sinag</i>	<i>Si-nar (stressed word/nar/)</i>	<i>Si-nar (Unstressed word /si/)</i>	<i>Sunrise</i>
<i>Pulao</i>	<i>Pulo</i>	<i>Pu-loa (stressed word/lo/)</i>	<i>Pu-lo (Unstressed word /pu)</i>	<i>Sail</i>
<i>Belimbing</i>	<i>Balimbing</i>	<i>Be-lim-bing (stressed word/lim/bng/)</i>	<i>Ba-lim-bing (stressed word/ba/)</i>	<i>Starfruit</i>

DISCUSSION

Table 1 and Table 2 show the alphabets of Tagalog and Bahasa Indonesia. Bahasa Indonesia has 26 letters, which are the widest spoken throughout Indonesia. However, the borrowed words of Dutch origins can be found in Indonesia. On the other hand, the colonialism of the Dutch, in purpose to elucidate thoughts about how their alphabet is pronounced, indicates the big influences. The two letters "Ñ" and "Ng," which are derived from Tagalog, the primary language spoken in the Philippines, are not discussed in this discussion. Bahasa Indonesian uses numeration of orthography, a method that is highly effective and does not involve controversy, to affect pronunciation with the aid of many loanwords from the Dutch colonization of the Philippines.

In Table 3, it shows that Spanish phonology has an impact on Tagalog phonology and colonization by Americans. The inventory of phonemic words of Filipinos increased due to the incorporation of several Spanish and English borrowed terms. This is shown in the change in pronunciation from three to five vowel systems within the language. /i/ and /e/, the vowels, were initially regarded as identical allophonic phonemes, whose situation with

the vowels /u/ was comparable and /o/ (Schachter & Reid, 2009 as cited in Arizo et al., 2020).

Table 4 illustrates the six vowel phonemes that are present in Indonesian language: the front high vowel /i/, the front medium vowel /e/, the central medium vowel /ə/, the central low vowel /a/, the medium high vowel /u/, and the back medium vowel /o/. The 22 consonant phonemes in Indonesian are categorized according to three criteria: the location and style of articulation, as well as the presence or absence of an open vocal cord (Wijana, 2003).

Table 5 contains the similar words in both Tagalog and Indonesian, along with their common meanings are highly accurate and precise. This list of similar meanings between Indonesian and Tagalog are closely related in terms of their phonology, despite on their different syllable structures, it can be furthermore found in dictionaries as well, considering the fact that Indonesian and Tagalog are the two most spoken languages in the Southeast Asian region. Moreover both languages belong to the Malayo-polynesian subgroup of the Austronesian language family.

Table 6 shows the similar syllable structure of both Indonesian and Tagalog words, resulting in a double meaning for each phonological word. The given list of meanings goes to show how they can be interpreted in terms of culture, behavior, and stress or unstressed syllables in communication. This impacts the responders' judgment or by the understanding of what said words have a similar pronunciation, but it can be further clarified and decoded by learning their syllable structure.

Table 7 shows the stress and unstressed syllable patterns of Indonesian and Tagalog phonological similarities with meanings. Stressed words often start at the beginning or at the end of each word's syllables with louder and greater emphasis than the other syllables, alternatively while the other is lower and less emphasis, which are the unstressed words. This involves our hearing and pronunciation, depending on where we put the stress or unstressed to our words. In Indonesia, mostly they put the stressed syllables at the end of the words, which is indicated in this figure. While Tagalog words are much unstressed, the '/' are markings of where the stressed or unstressed syllables are used or placed.

The Phonology as Human Behavior (PHB) framework provides a clear foundation for the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. Phonologically speaking, Tagalog and Indonesian are similar in how they communicate in daily life. It suggests that during a discussion, Tagalog and Indonesian can still deliver correct sound responses. According to its definition, Phonology as Human Behavior (PHB) is the study of how words or concepts are actually spoken in order to facilitate effective communication. The way that two languages are used in daily communication shapes their phonological similarities, which are evident in the Philippines and Indonesia, where Tagalog and Indonesian use Phonology as Human Behavior (PHB) to examine their phonological similarities. This is likely the reason that Tagalog and Indonesian share a common usage

of words and accurate pronunciations, as they are members of the same family—the Austronesian family.

William Diver (1979) asserts that the notion of phonology as human behavior (PHB) can be used to simplify a language in order to investigate its phonological similarities. According to William Diver, analyzing stress patterns and the way both languages employ syllable structures would provide a more comprehensive knowledge of how important and potent sound is for efficient communication. This idea offers a thorough explanation of the relationship between the phonetic similarities between Indonesian and Tagalog. For example, the “Goat” is mostly known as “Kambing” in the Philippines, while in Indonesia “Kambing” also refers to “Goat” which means an animal who eats leaves, soft shoots, or fruits of high-growing plants, shrubs and trees. However, it is considered as shared Phonological behavior of two different languages.

To provide straight-forward responses to the research questions. Using the discussion above, it was able to respond to the question of how the phonological similarities between two languages provided a thorough phonetics for efficient communication together with the notion of phonology as human behavior. This raises the research question of how to pronounce Tagalog and Indonesian correctly from a communication standpoint. William Diver's Phonology as Human Behaviour (PHB) is a useful tool for figuring out whether two different languages have phonological similarities. The research demonstrated that when communicating a sound, Tagalog and Indonesian had phonological similarities. As said, there is no evidence to support the claim that the phonological characteristics of two distinct languages influence how well they interact and produce sounds during conversation.

Conclusions

To sum up this study, Tagalog and Indonesian possessed phonological similarities within the lens of phonology as human behavior (PHB) as a tool for analysis. It explains some of the phonological similarities between two different languages. This paper offers a comprehensive explanation of why Tagalog and Indonesian possessed phonological similarities in terms of syllable structures and sound patterns during a conversation. Above-mentioned, the phonological behavior of Tagalog and Indonesian is truly similar due to the fact that they belong to the Austronesian group. Tagalog and Indonesian shared phonological similarities uniquely.

This study provides a response to whether Tagalog and Indonesian possess phonological similarities. Based on the literature review and results, it is concluded that Tagalog and Indonesian share some similarities in language. The idea that they are linguistically similar is due to the phonological behavior that both languages adopt loanwords from different colonizers, causing them to become similar and able to possess a similar way of conveying a sound in a conversation. This phonological behavior of Tagalog and Indonesian is linguistically unique. They are more likely similar due to the strong relations. As stated above, both Indonesia and the Philippines are archipelagic nations with a

similar ethnic population of Austronesian descent. The Philippines and ancient Indonesia have a long history dating back to the 9th century. Tagalog is a well-known descendant of the Malayo-Polynesian subgroup.

Recommendations

With these findings, future researchers who seek an answer to the phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian can now clearly figure out the phonological behavior of two different languages. This finding can surely guide future language researchers to have a broad understanding of how Tagalog and Indonesian pronounced and produced a sound. Since there is very limited research about the phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian explaining the phonological behavior in terms of the phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian, these findings can be a starting point of linguistic behavior research in both the Philippines and Indonesia. In addition, language or linguistics teachers in the Philippines and Indonesia can use this finding to explore and examine the phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian to encourage students and researchers to improve their knowledge about the shared commonalities of two different languages. This finding can help persuade Filipino and Indonesian students, as well as the linguistic teachers, to develop a comprehensive understanding of the phonological similarities of Tagalog and Indonesian.

This paper can be a guide for linguistic researchers to better comprehend the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesian. This paper is not only for Filipino students and linguistic teachers; other foreign students, like Indonesian students, and researchers can benefit from this paper. Filipino and Indonesian linguistics students will benefit from this paper the most because in the Philippines and Indonesian linguistics research, the research with this scope of problem is very limited. This study can help attract future researchers to have this kind of interest. In the Philippines and Indonesia, as well as the Asian countries, there are not enough studies about the phonological similarities between Tagalog and Indonesia. That is why this study can be a head start to producing more papers about the linguistic behavior of different nations.

This research is highly recommended to future researchers from both Tagalog and foreign linguistic students, as well as the linguistic teachers, to have an in-depth overview of the shared phonological commonalities of Tagalog and Indonesian.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers complied with the ethical standards in conducting the textual analysis. The researchers have no conflict of interest and bias in any way, honesty was highly applied during the analysis of the data.

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